

Electro kinetic fractal dimension for characterizing Shajara reservoirs of the Shajara Formation

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Abstract

The quality and assessment of a reservoir can be documented in details by the application of electro kinetic. This research aims to calculate fractal dimension from the relationship among electro kinetic, maximum electro kinetic and wetting phase saturation and to confirm it by the fractal dimension derived from the relationship among capillary pressure and wetting phase saturation. In this research, porosity was measured on real collected sandstone samples and permeability was calculated theoretically from capillary pressure profile measured by mercury intrusion contaminating the pores of sandstone samples in consideration. Two equations for calculating the fractal dimensions have been employed. The first one describes the functional relationship between wetting phase saturation, electro kinetic, maximum electro kinetic coefficient and fractal dimension. The second equation implies to the wetting phase saturation as a function of capillary pressure and the fractal dimension. Two procedures for obtaining the fractal dimension have been utilized. The first procedure was done by plotting the logarithm of the ratio between electro kinetic and maximum electro kinetic versus logarithm wetting phase saturation. The slope of the first procedure = $3 - D_f$ (fractal dimension). The second procedure for obtaining the fractal dimension was concluded by plotting the logarithm of capillary pressure versus the logarithm of wetting phase saturation. The slope of the second procedure = $D_f - 3$. On the basis of the obtained results of the fabricated stratigraphic column and the attained values of the fractal dimension, the sandstones of the Shajara reservoirs of the Shajara Formation were divided here into three units. The gained units from bottom to top are: Lower Shajara electro kinetic Fractal Dimension Unit, Middle Shajara electro kinetic Fractal dimension Unit, and Upper Shajara electro kinetic Fractal Dimension Unit. The results show similarity between electrical potential gradient fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension. It was also noted that samples with wide range of pore radius were characterized by high values of fractal dimensions due to an increase in their connectivities. In our case, and as conclusions the higher the fractal dimension, the higher the heterogeneity, the higher the permeability, the better the reservoir characteristics.

Keywords: Shajara reservoirs, Shajara Formation, Electro kinetic fractal dimension

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Introduction

An increase of electro kinetic coupling coefficient with increasing permeability that can explain by the effect of variation in surface conductivity was examined by.^[1] The reduction of streaming potential coefficient during compaction suggests that the tortuosity of the hydraulic network increases faster than tortuosity of the electric network was reported by.^[2] An increase of streaming potential coupling coefficient with increasing permeability was demonstrated by.^[3] A new method to calculate total electric conductivity from the ratio of pore area cross-section to length of the effective rock capillaries which derived from streaming potential measurements was investigated by.^[4] Capillary pressure follows the scaling law at low water saturation was reported by.^[5] Streaming potential coupling coefficient measurements to monitor flow in saline surface environments such as deep saline aquifers and hydrocarbon reservoirs was studied by.^[6] Electro kinetic relationship to produce a function that links the mean grain size of a rock to its effective mean pore radius was described by.^[7] An increase of volumetric flow rate, which, in turn, increases the penetration distance of the acid before it is being spent due to application of direct current to improve acidizing operations was investigated by.^[8] A novel method for estimating permeability with streaming current and electro osmosis pressure was developed by.^[9] Good agreement between electro kinetically deduced and gas

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measured permeability was presented by.^[10] An increase of bubble pressure fractal dimension and pressure head fractal dimension with decreasing pore size distribution index and fitting parameters $m \times n$ due to possibility of having inter connected channels was proofed by.^[11] An increase of fractal dimension with increasing permeability, relaxation time of induced polarization, due to an increase in pore connectivity was confirmed by.^[12]

Materials and Methods

Samples were collected from the Surface type section of the Shajara Reservoirs of Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation, latitude 26° 52' 17.4,"longitude 43° 36' 18" (Figure 1). Porosity was measured and permeability was calculated from the measured capillary pressure data obtained by mercury intrusion technique on powder sandstone samples. Pore radius was determined from distribution of pores which enables the calculation of electro kinetic fractal dimension.

The electro kinetic fractal dimension can be scaled as

$$S_w = \left[\frac{CEK^{\frac{1}{4}}}{CEK_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right]^{[3-Df]} \quad 1$$

Where S_w the water saturation, CEK the electro kinetic coefficient in ampere / (pascal * meter), CEK_{max} the maximum electro kinetic coefficient in ampere /(pascal * meter), and Df the fractal dimension. Equation 1 can be proofed from

$$V = CEK * E \quad 2$$

Where V the flow velocity in meter / second, CEK the electro kinetic coefficient in ampere / (pascal* meter). E the electric field in volt / meter.

The flow velocity can be scaled as

$$V = \left[\frac{Q}{A} \right] \quad 3$$

Where V the flow velocity in meter / second, Q the flow rate in cubic meter / second, A the area in square meter.

Insert equation 3 into equation 2

$$\left[\frac{Q}{A} \right] = CEK * E \quad 4$$

The flow rate can be scaled as

$$Q = \left[\frac{\pi * r^4 * \Delta p}{8 * \mu * L} \right] \quad 5$$

Where Q the flow rate in cubic meter / second, r the pore radius in meter, Δp the differential pressure in pascal, μ the fluid viscosity, L the capillary length in meter.

Insert equation 5 into equation 4

$$\left[\frac{\pi * r^4 * \Delta p}{8 * \mu * L * A} \right] = CEK * E \quad 6$$

Equation 6 after rearrangement will become

$$r^4 = \left[\frac{8 * \mu * L * A * CEK * E}{\pi * \Delta p} \right] \quad 7$$

The maximum pore radius can be scaled as

$$r_{max}^4 = \left[\frac{8 * \mu * L * A * CEK_{max} * E}{\pi * \Delta p} \right] \quad 8$$

Divide equation 7 by equation 8

$$\left[\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} \right] = \left[\frac{8 * \mu * L * A * CEK * E}{8 * \mu * L * A * CEK_{max} * E} \right] \quad 9$$

Equation 9 after simplification will become

$$\left[\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} \right] = \left[\frac{CEK}{CEK_{max}} \right] \quad 10$$

Take the fourth root of equation 10

$$\sqrt[4]{\left[\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} \right]} = \sqrt[4]{\left[\frac{CEK}{CEK_{max}} \right]} \quad 11$$

Equation 11 after simplification will become

$$\left[\frac{r}{r_{max}} \right] = \left[\frac{CEK^{\frac{1}{4}}}{CEK_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right] \quad 12$$

Take the logarithm of equation 12

$$\log \left[\frac{r}{r_{max}} \right] = \log \left[\frac{CEK^{\frac{1}{4}}}{CEK_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right] \quad 13$$

$$\text{But; } \log \left[\frac{r}{r_{max}} \right] = \frac{\log S_w}{[3 - Df]} \quad 14$$

Insert equation 14 into equation 13

$$\frac{\log S_w}{[3 - Df]} = \log \left[\frac{CEK^{\frac{1}{4}}}{CEK_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right] \quad 15$$

Equation 15 after log removal will become

$$S_w = \left[\frac{CEK^{\frac{1}{4}}}{CEK_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right]^{[3-Df]} \quad 16$$

Equation 16 the proof of equation 1 which relates the water saturation, electro kinetic coefficient, maximum electro kinetic coefficient, and the fractal dimension. The capillary pressure can be scaled as

$$S_w = [D_f - 3] * P_c + \text{constant} \quad 17$$

Where S_w the water saturation, D_f the fractal dimension, P_c the capillary pressure.

Results and Discussion

Based on field observation the Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation were divided here into three units as described in (Figure 1). These units from bottom to top are: Lower, Middle and Upper Shajara Reservoir. Their developed results of electro kinetic and capillary fractal dimensions are presented in (Table 1). The results show equalities between electro kinetic fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension. A maximum fractal dimension value of about 2.7872 was informed from sample SJ13 as demonstrated in (Table 1). But, a minimum fractal dimension value 2.4379 allocates to sample SJ3 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir as defined in (Table

1). The electro kinetic and capillary pressure fractal dimensions were observed to increase with increasing permeability owing to the possibility of having interconnected channels as verified in (Table 1). Regarding the Lower Shajara Reservoir, it is represented by six sandstone samples as shown in (Figure 1), four of which label as SJ1, SJ2, SJ3, and SJ4 were selected for capillary pressure measurements to determine the fractal dimension. Their positive slopes of the first procedure (log ratio of electro kinetic to maximum electro kinetic versus log water saturation (S_w)) and negative slopes of the second procedure (log capillary pressure (P_c) versus log water saturation (S_w)) were described in (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5 and Table 1). Their electro kinetic fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension values are shown in Table 1. As we progress from sample SJ2 to SJ3 a noticeable reduction in permeability from 1955 md to 56 md was observed due to compaction which reflects change in electro kinetic fractal dimension from 2.7748 to 2.4379 as delineated in (Table 1). Such drastic change in permeability can account for heterogeneity which is a key parameter in reservoir quality assessment. Once more, an increase in grain size and permeability was reported from sample SJ4 whose electro kinetic fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension was found to be 2.6843 as illustrated in (Table 1).

Figure 1: Surface type section of the Shajara reservoirs of the Shajara Formation, at latitude 26° 52 ' 17.4'' longitude 43° 36 '18 ''

Figure 2: Log (CEK1/4 / CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ1

Figure 3: Log (CEK1/4 / CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ2

Figure 4: Log (CEK1/4 / CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ3

Figure 5: Log (CEK1/4 / CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ4

Formation	Reservoir	Sample	Porosity %	k (md)	Positive slope of the first procedure Slope=3-Df	Negative slope of the second procedure Slope=Df-3	Electro kinetic fractal dimension	Capillary pressure fractal dimension
Perno-Carboniferous Shajara Formation	Upper Shajara Reservoir	SJ13	25	973	0.2128	-0.2128	2.7872	2.7872
		SJ12	28	1440	0.2141	-0.2141	2.7859	2.7859
		SJ11	36	1197	0.2414	-0.2414	2.7586	2.7586
	Middle Shajara Reservoir	SJ9	31	1394	0.2214	-0.2214	2.7786	2.7786
		SJ8	32	1344	0.2248	-0.2248	2.7752	2.7752
		SJ7	35	1472	0.2317	-0.2317	2.7683	2.7683
	Lower Shajara Reservoir	SJ4	30	176	0.3157	-0.3157	2.6843	2.6843
		SJ3	34	56	0.5621	-0.5621	2.4379	2.4379
		SJ2	35	1955	0.2252	-0.2252	2.7748	2.7748
		SJ1	29	1680	0.2141	-0.2141	2.7859	2.7859

Table 1: Petrophysical model showing the three Shajara Reservoir Units with their corresponding values of electro kinetic fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension

Concerning the Middle Shajara Reservoir, it is separated from Lower Shajara Reservoir by an unconformity surface as shown in (Figure 1). It was represented by four samples, three of which named as SJ7, SJ8, and SJ9 were selected for fractal dimension determination as verified in (Table 1). Their positive and negative slopes of the first and second procedures were described in (Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8 and (Table 1) Additionally, their electro kinetic and capillary pressure fractal dimension displays equal values as shown in (Table 1) Moreover, their fractal dimension values are higher than those of sample SJ3 and SJ4 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir due to an increase in their permeability as specified in (Table 1). On the other hand, the Upper Shajara reservoir is separated from the Middle Shajara reservoir by yellow green mudstone as revealed in (Figure 1). It is defined by three samples so called SJ11, SJ12, SJ13 as explained in (Table 1). Their

positive slopes of the first procedure and negative slopes of the second procedure are displayed in (Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11 and Table 1). Moreover, their electro kinetic fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension are also higher than those of sample SJ3 and SJ4 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir due to an increase in their permeability as testified in (Table 1). Overall a plot of positive slope of the first procedure versus negative slope of the second procedure delineates three reservoir zones of varying petrophysical characteristics as shown in (Figure 12). These zones were also confirmed by plotting electro kinetic fractal dimension versus capillary pressure fractal dimension as shown in (Figure 13). Such variation in fractal dimensions can be used to explain heterogeneity which is a key parameter in reservoir quality assessment.

Figure 6: Log (CEK1/4 /CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ7

Figure 7: Log (CEK1/4 /CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ8

Figure 8: Log (CEK1/4 /CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ9

Figure 9: Log (CEK1/4 /CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ11

Figure 10: Log (CEK1/4/CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ12

Figure 11: Log (CEK1/4/CEK1/4max) versus log Sw & log Pc versus log Sw for sample SJ13

Figure 12: Positive slope of the first procedure versus negative slope of the second procedure

Figure 13: Electro kinetic fractal dimension versus capillary pressure fractal dimension

Conclusions

The sandstones of the Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation were divided here into three units based on electro kinetic fractal. The Units from bottom to top are Lower Shajara electro kinetic fractal dimension unit, Middle Shajara electro kinetic fractal dimension unit, and Upper Shajara electro kinetic fractal dimension unit. These units were also confirmed by capillary pressure fractal dimension. The heterogeneity increases with increasing permeability, increasing fractal dimension, decreasing compaction owing to possibility of having interconnected channels.

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